

Yield of Molecular Hydrogen as a Criterion for the Radiation Stability of Organic Compounds*

ADNAN A. KARIM AL-DHAHIR

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Al-Fateh University, Tripoli, Libyan Arab Republic

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The fate of *n*-hexane molecule labelled by hot recoiling tritium atom was experimentally studied in liquid and solid phases, with and without iodine ($5 \times 10^{-3} M$) as thermal free radicals scavenger. The addition of such micro amount of iodine did not appreciably reduce the yields of tritium-labelled hot interaction products. So is the case with light hydrocarbons. The same amount of iodine had no effect upon these yields in the solid state. Tritium-labelled ethylene yield has therefore been taken as a measure of the degree of stability of labelled and excited *n*-hexane molecule. The yield of C_6H_5T was small to indicate that $>90\%$ of $n-C_6H_{11}T$ and HT are formed in the hot region of interaction between T atom and *n*-hexane molecule; the interaction is too fast to allow displacement of one hydrogen atom by one tritium one or the abstraction of the first by the second to be significantly affected by a third object like iodine. The "residual" excitation energy in *n*-hexane-T molecule is too small and does not cause its disintegration. The yield of labelled ethylene product is very small and indicates that very few highly excited $n-C_6H_{11}T$ molecules disintegrate immediately after formation. Formation of HT and $n-C_6H_{11}T$ molecules follows different mechanisms. Hence HT yield could not serve as a measure for the stabilization and survival of $n-C_6H_{11}T$ molecules, since the first does not form at the expense of the second.

It has been stated that the yield of molecular hydrogen as a radiation product serves as a good measure of the extent to which an organic compound can withstand the action of ionizing or electro-magnetic radiation¹⁻⁶. The same idea was wrongly transferred to the field of hot atom chemistry which is very close to radiation chemistry. As a result, scientists started talking about a molecular hydrogen of the form HT instead of H_2 .

The principal aim of this research was to demonstrate experimentally that the yield of labelled olefines (but not HT) is the real measure of the extent to which *n*-hexane molecule survives after getting labelled by one tritium atom.

Experimental

Detectors: A conventional radio gas chromatography system was used^{7,8,9}. It consisted of two detectors:

- (i) a gas flow proportional counter which registered β radiation passing through it with the carrier gas (helium). The corresponding β energy spectrum was converted to peaks. The area of each peak is proportional to the total activity of the corresponding compound labelled by tritium atom;
- (ii) the second detecting system being an ordinary cathatometer with sensitive thermistors.

Columns: To carry out analysis of liquid-phase products, a 4-meter copper column 5 mm i.d. was

used. It was packed with diatomite (0.25-0.50 mesh) coated with 10% w/w dioctylphthalate as the stationary phase. Oven temperature was $80 \pm 1^\circ$. Helium was the carrier gas.

Analyses of gas-phase products were carried out with 2 or 4 meter (5 mm i.d.) copper columns packed with silica gel at different temperatures (room, 100 and 200°).

Irradiation: Two fluxes of thermal neutrons were used:

- (i) Liquid-phase samples: a thermal flux of 1.2×10^{13} neutrons/sec/cm² at 70° . Time of irradiation, 15 min.
- (ii) Solid-state samples: a thermal flux of 9×10^{11} neutrons/sec/cm² at -170° . Time of irradiation, 2 hr.

Source of neutrons: A nuclear reactor type ERT - 1000.

Samples: 20 μ l samples of *n*-hexane were placed in 4 cm long and 3 mm diameter quartz ampoules along with 20 μ g lithium carbonate. Ampoules were evacuated (10^{-4} torr) after being frozen in liquid nitrogen (-196°) and sealed with the aid of an oxygen flame.

Results and Discussion

To discuss the main question of the stabilization of tritium labelled organic compounds in liquid state, and the role and the nature of the second constituent, it is important to note that the

* This work was done at the Department of Radiochemistry, Moscow State University, Moscow, USSR.

yield of HT gas, as the major product in most cases, cannot serve as an evidence for the presence of any kind of "protection" of one molecule over the other.

This is true since the formation of a large part of HT gas takes place by a fast single-step abstraction of one hydrogen atom by a hot tritium atom (having a high kinetic energy) resulting in the instantaneous evolution of HT molecule^{10,11}.

This process takes place so fast that nothing can affect its occurrence. There is a total agreement on this.

Yield of HT gas from *n*-hexane was 53.4% (Table 1). At least 90% of this yield was formed by this mechanism.

	HT	C ₁ -C ₆ <i>n</i> -hexane-T	light polymer-T	heavy polymer-T
liquid phase	53.4	10.7	28.9	2.5
liquid phase + iodine	51.2	10.2	26.9	7.9
solid phase with and without iodine	45.6	14.3	33	2.7
				4.4

What is therefore the alternative criterion which might be taken as a measure for the stability and for the defending (protecting) effect as well? It is the yield of the original irradiated system itself labelled by tritium and the total yield of labelled C-C bonds rupture taking place in the labelled parent molecule (C₆H₁₃T).

What happens to a *n*-hexane molecule just labelled by a hot tritium atom formed as a result of the nuclear reaction

Once tritium atom is in the hot stage at the instant of the reaction, the interaction of tritium with *n*-hexane molecule should take place by the fast single-step displacement of one hydrogen atom giving rise to an excited *n*-C₆H₁₃T molecule. Such a molecule either stabilizes* or decomposes.

Decomposition of an excited n-C₆H₁₃T molecule : C-C bond breakage :

The decomposition can occur via the following possible route :

* HT and *n*-hexane-T yields comprise 80-82% of the total labelled products in the liquid phase (Table 1).

Unlabelled paraffines can be formed according to the following radical recombination processes :

Olefines :

Olefinic products seem to be the sole products of any disintegration process of an excited hexane molecule caused by C-C bond breakage. In other words, neither HT nor labelled paraffinic compounds help as a measure of the stability of this excited molecule.

Other types of decompositions :

Our separation conditions and many other considerations did not allow for a full tracing of labelled hexane (C₆H₁₁T). This product might be a consequence of a stabilization process of a labelled and excited hexane molecule by the liberation of one hydrogen molecule^{9,12} according to the following scheme :

Therefore C-C bond rupture model remains the unique stability criterion.

Our gas-phase assay did not show any evidence of the presence of light labelled olefines such as propene or butene though susceptibility of the set up and column conditions were absolutely capable to detect any trace of them.

Formation of labelled paraffines should, therefore, be a sequence of a substantially different mechanism. This mechanism must be relatively easier since C₁-C₆ labelled paraffines were always detected in all experiments. The following mecha-

nism accounts for the formation of such products : abstraction of an alkyl group by a hot tritium atom as a result of a fast localized attack at a C-C bond with the immediate formation of either the lighter alkane (CH₃T) or the heavier one (C₂H₅T). Table 2 shows that yields of CH₃T and of C₂H₅T are 3.5 and 2 times that of C₆H₁₁T respectively.

TABLE 2—PERCENT YIELD OF C₁-C₆ LABELLED HYDROCARBONS

	CH ₃ T	C ₂ H ₅ T	C ₃ H ₇ T	C ₄ H ₉ T	C ₅ H ₁₁ T	Total
liquid phase	3.77	1.93	0.58	1.29	2.12	1.01
liquid phase + iodine	3.3	1.64	0.32	1.37	2.74	0.91
solid phase with and without iodine	4.65	2.32	0.55	1.07	3.58	2.13

Moreover, radicals such as C_3H_6T (step 4) can combine with a free hydrogen radical H° to form the corresponding alkane :

This suggests that the moderately excited radical C_3H_6T cools down after several collisions with different surrounding species. As a result, it loses the excess energy of excitation (which could be vibrational or rotational in this stage) and thus survives rather than decomposes. This could be a further explanation of the previous question of why did labelled alkanes were always formed in considerable amounts, while just one labelled alkane (ethylene) was detected in our circumstances (Table 2).

Conclusions :

1. There is no way to avoid the formation of HT gas from a "hot" interaction of tritium with hexane molecule. The exact percentage yield of $C_6H_{13}T$ which undergoes disproportionation is unknown, since the addition of iodine ($5 \times 10^{-3}M$) reduced the yield of hexane-T very slightly (about 4%). This would imply that a very small part of hexane-T was formed by the addition of thermal tritons most likely to C_6H_{13} radicals left after the direct formation of HT.

2. Difference between types of interactions of different bombarding radiations (γ , fast electrons, and thermal neutrons for instance) should be taken into consideration. Nature of each kind of radiation inevitably gives rise to different modes of interactions.
3. Labelled olefines are the sole measure for the stability of an excited and tritium labelled *n*-hexane molecule.

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